

Non-isothermal solid state reaction kinetics of sol-gel derived zirconium phosphate from thermogravimetric data

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Abstract : Thermal transformation of polyvalent zirconium phosphate containing alpha and gamma zirconium phosphate as crystalline phases has drawn immense scientific and industrial attention in deriving advanced materials such as selective ion exchanger, acid catalyst, protonic conductor, glass-ceramic and novel functionalized ceramic. Thermal transformation of sol-gel derived zirconium phosphate was studied employing simultaneous differential thermal analysis (TG-DTA) in static air at different heating rates 5, 7.5 and 10 K min⁻¹ respectively. Kinetics of multistage transformation of synthesized zirconium phosphate under non-isothermal condition were interpreted and correlated by isoconversional Flynn-Wall-Ozawa (FWO) and model-free Kissinger methods. Kinetic parameters like pre-exponential factor and activation energy for conversion computed by both the methods were observed well consistent although FWO method exhibited more reliability and accuracy. Malek method was used to elucidate the thermal decomposition mechanism of synthesized zirconium phosphate. The research results showed that the transformation of synthetic zirconium phosphate under non-isothermal condition was governed by contracting volume kinetic mechanism.

Keywords : Zirconium phosphate, non-isothermal decomposition, thermogravimetry, kinetics, reaction mechanism.

Introduction

Zirconium phosphates constitute an important class of polyvalent metal compound that may exist in two basic forms such as alpha and gamma zirconium phosphate represented by formulae α -Zr(HPO₄)₂.H₂O and γ -Zr(PO₄)(H₂PO₄).2H₂O respectively. The polyvalent phosphates of zirconium can be transformed readily into advanced materials on thermal treatment which find potential applications as selective ion exchanger, heterogeneous catalyst, protonic conductor, glass ceramic and novel functionalized ceramic¹.

The compound was first prepared by Clearfield and Stynes¹ using reflux technique. Carriere *et al.*² synthesized alpha zirconium phosphate crystal via sol-gel method. Later, Alberti *et al.*³ derived alpha zirconium phosphate with high degree of crystallinity by direct precipitation – the so-called fluorine complex method. Tarafdar *et al.*⁴ prepared spherical mesostructured zirconium phosphate by solution-precipitation method in presence of tetradecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide in alkaline medium using zirconium carbonate and NH₄H₂PO₄ as starting materi-

als. Wu *et al.*⁵ obtained pure ammonium zirconium phosphate [NH₄ZrH(PO₄)₂.H₂O] phase via solid-state reaction at low temperature using zirconium oxychloride and di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as raw materials which behaved excellently as heterogeneous catalyst in the synthesis of butyl acetate. Thermal decomposition of the ammonium zirconium phosphate compound experienced four steps consisting of three endothermic peaks and an exothermic peak. These changes were attributed to dehydration of crystal water molecule, deamination, intramolecular dehydration of protonated phosphate groups and formation of orthorhombic zirconium pyrophosphate respectively. Based on FWO and Kissinger equation, the average activation energies corresponding to the four steps of thermal decomposition and crystallization of pyrophosphate were reported as 56.720 ± 13.1, 106.55 ± 6.28, 129.25 ± 4.32 and 521.90 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The non-isothermal dehydration kinetics of AlPO₄.2H₂O by TG-DTG-DTA method at different heating rates exhibited two step reactions in the temperature range 80–150 °C. The activation energy for the second dehydra-

tion reaction of AlPO_4 calculated by Kissinger method was found to be $69.68 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.⁶

A thorough study on the non-isothermal decomposition kinetics of zirconium phosphates at different heating rates provides useful technological data for controlling the course of reaction, optimization of process condition, understanding of the thermal decomposition mechanism and more specifically the nature and thermal stability of end product.

In the present investigation, mechanism and kinetics of thermal transformation of synthesized zirconium phosphate were studied using TG-DTA technology under non-isothermal condition with different heating rates. The non-isothermal decomposition kinetics of zirconium phosphate were interpreted and correlated by Flynn-Wall-Ozawa^{7,8} method and Kissinger method⁹. The non-isothermal transformation mechanism of zirconium phosphate was ascertained by Malek method^{10,11}.

Experimental

The sol-gel derived zirconium phosphate hydrogel has been chosen as starting material for the non-isothermal decomposition study. All the chemicals such as $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and ortho phosphoric acid used in the study were of analytical grade reagent (E. Merck). Ultrafine zirconium phosphate in the molar ratio of $\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 = 1 : 1.5$ was synthesized by sol-gel route through aqueous phase interaction of requisite amount of 0.5(M) zirconium oxychloride ($\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and 4(N) H_3PO_4 with vigorous stirring until gelation was complete at pH 2.5. The whole mass was further stirred for 2 h at room temperature with a magnetic stirrer. The gel mass was then allowed to age for 24 h. The formed gel was filtered through Whatman-40 filter paper under suction and washed thoroughly with the hot distilled water to remove dissolved impurities. The filter cake was then bone dried in an air oven at $110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h and pulverized. The powdered sample (-30 B.S mesh) was stored in an incubator at $35 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The finely agated sample was chemically analysed with respect to chemical constituents following standard method. The specific surface area of the dried gel powder was measured based on low temperature N_2 adsorption BET principle. Infrared analysis of dried precursor was recorded in KBr phase by FTIR spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer-783) in the frequency region $4000\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

for isolating the nature of bond. For identification of crystalline phases of heat treated sample, X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was carried out by Phillips automatic X-ray diffractometer (X'Pert PRO PW-3071). Ni-filtered $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$, 40 KV and 20 mA radiations of 1.5405 \AA was employed at a scanning rate of 2° min^{-1} . The thermal behavior of the gel mass was examined by simultaneous differential thermal analysis (TG-DTA) using Netzch STA 409C thermal analyser at three different heating rates of 5, 7.5 and 10 K min^{-1} respectively in static air up to $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The zirconium phosphate was taken in the form of loose powder for thermal study and pure $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder was used as reference sample. Afterwards, morphology of precursor powder dried at $110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and heat treated at $965 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ were studied by scanning electron microscopy (Quanta 200, FEI make, Holland).

Finally, key kinetic parameters of thermal decomposition were calculated from the TG data of dried precursor powder applying FWO and Kissinger methods respectively.

Results and discussion

The physico-chemical properties of zirconium phosphate hydrogel powder were given in the Table 1. The opaque nature of the synthesized zirconium phosphate gel powder resulted from the finer particle sizes and random orientation of the microfine particles. The specific surface area of gel precursor was found as high as 149.7

Table 1. Physico-chemical characteristics of synthesized zirconium phosphate hydrogel powder

Properties	
Texture	Opaque white
$\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ molar ratio	1 : 1.5
Loose bulk density (g cm^{-3})	0.733
Specific surface area by	
BET ($\text{m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$)	149.7
DTA peak temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	125 (endo), 964.6 (exo)
Loss on ignition (wt. %)	19.8
FTIR spectra (cm^{-1})	3429.55, 1404.2, 1147.7, 1111, 1049.3, 1016.5, 746.5, 653.9, 603, 549.7
Crystallinity :	
As prepared gel	Crystalline
Calcined at $125 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Amorphous
Calcined at $964 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Well crystalline

$\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ indicating fine state of subdivision of the formed hydrogel. The typical chemical analysis of the precursor showed the molar ratio for $\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ as 1 : 1.5, thereby confirming total interaction of the ingredients and complete transformation into zirconium phosphate hydrogel at pH 2.5.

FT-IR spectra of dried zirconium phosphate precursor were shown in Fig. 1. Vibrational bands were identified in terms of HPO_4^{2-} and H_2O units. Broad absorption band in the region 3430 cm^{-1} attributed to the stretching vibration of -OH groups bonded to the surface of the molecule. No major peak for unbound moisture was noticed in the molecule. The appearance of strong absorption peak at 1627.9 cm^{-1} was due to bending vibration of -OH groups in the molecule. The intense FT-IR absorption peaks in the region $1147\text{--}1045 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was attributed to chelate complexes of PO_4 and ZrO_2 , P_2O_7 , $(\text{ZrO})_2\text{PO}_2\text{H}$ or $\text{ZrO}_2\text{PO}_2\text{H}$ species. In the region of $449\text{--}654 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, bands of PO_3 deformation and rocking modes as well as POP deformation and torsional modes were observed.

The TG-DTA curves (Figs. 2–4) of synthetic zirconium phosphate at three heating rates exhibited one well defined endothermic peak at around $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and single sharp exothermic peak at about $955 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The endothermic

peak at around $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was assigned to dehydration and dehydroxylation of gamma zirconium phosphate, $\gamma\text{-Zr}(\text{PO}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ through stepwise removal of crystal water leading to formation of amorphous zirconium phosphate. However, amorphous zirconium phosphate ultimately converted to crystalline ZrP_2O_7 at and above $955 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The weight losses of dehydration and dehydroxylation were recorded as 15.5% and 4.32% respectively which appeared well consistent with the theoretical values of gamma zirconium phosphate decomposition. The TG curves showed a total mass loss of 19.62% in the entire temperature range up to $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ which was in good agreement with the following stepwise dehydration sequence of gamma zirconium phosphate⁵ :

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectra of zirconium phosphate hydrogel precursor.

Fig. 2. TG-DTA curves of zirconium phosphate precursor at heating rate 5.0 °C/min.

Fig. 3. TG-DTA curves of zirconium phosphate precursor at heating rate 7.5 °C/min.

The powder XRD patterns of as prepared and heat treated synthesized zirconium phosphate also corroborated the above sequence of crystallographic transformation which showed micro-crystallinity upto 120 °C,

Fig. 4. TG-DTA curve of zirconium phosphate precursor at heating rate 10.0 °C/min.

changed to X-Ray amorphous in the temperature range 120–955 °C and finally crystallized to ZrP_2O_7 above 955 °C (XRD pattern not given)

Methods of determining dynamic kinetic parameters are discussed below :

Thermogravimetric analysis is one of the most commonly used technique to study the primary reaction of dehydration of crystalline solid :

Weight loss data at a given temperature is converted to a normalized form called conversion fraction (α). The reaction rate can be expressed by the degree of conversion (α) according to the formula :

$$\alpha = (m_i - m_t)/(m_i - m_f) \quad (1)$$

where m_i , m_f and m_t are the initial, final and current sample mass at the moment t during thermogravimetric analysis, respectively.

(i) *Activation energy and pre-exponential factor by Flynn-Wall-Ozawa method^{7,8} :*

Flynn, Wall and Ozawa independently develop an isoconversional calculation method by using Doyle approximation from non-isothermal data which is commonly

referred to as the FWO method. Rate of reaction of solid-state decomposition can be expressed by the following general equation :

$$d\alpha/dt = A.e^{-E_a/RT}.f(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

When heating rate is kept fixed, that is : $\beta = dT/dt$, eq. (2) can be rewritten as,

$$d\alpha/dT = A/\beta.e^{-E_a/RT}.f(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

where E_a is the apparent activation energy (kJ mol^{-1}), A is the pre-exponential factor (s^{-1}), R is the universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), $f(\alpha)$ is a differential form of reaction model which reveals the mechanism of reaction. By a series of transforms, eq. (3) can be rewritten as follows :

$$\log \beta = [\log E_a/R - \log g(\alpha) - 2.315] - 0.4567 E_a/RT \quad (4)$$

where $g(\alpha)$ is the integrated form of reaction model. If α is a fixed value, then $\log g(\alpha)$ is a fixed value too. The plot of $\log \beta$ against $1/T$ must give rise to a master straight line. Thus, activation energy E_a of the reaction can be obtained from linear slope ($k = -0.4567E_a/R$), irrespective of the $g(\alpha)$ employed.

(ii) *Activation energy and pre-exponential factor by Kissinger method⁹ :*

Kissinger method is a model-free approach as it does

not require any model-related assumptions to calculate E_a . According to the DTA curve and the Kissinger equation (eq. (5)), the activation energy and pre-exponential factor of thermal decomposition reaction can be computed as follows.

$$\ln \beta/T_{\max}^2 = -E_a/RT_{\max} + \ln AR/E_a \quad (5)$$

where β is the heating rate (K min^{-1}), T_{\max} is the most rapidly decomposing temperature corresponding to maximum reaction rate (peak temperature on DTA curve, K), E_a is the activation energy (kJ mol^{-1}) of thermal decomposition, R is the universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and A is the pre-exponential factor (s^{-1}).

The plot of $\ln \beta/T_{\max}^2$ versus $1/T_{\max}^2$ gives rise to a master straight line from which reaction activation energy E_a can be determined from the linear slope ($k = -E_a/R$), and the pre-exponential factor A from the linear intercept [$h = \ln (AR/E_a)$].

(iii) *Decomposition mechanism by Malek method*^{10,11} :

The Malek method^{10,11} is used to determine the most probable mechanism of decomposition reaction where the standard curve equation of mechanism function is depicted by :

$$y(\alpha) = f(\alpha) F(\alpha)/f(0.5) F(0.5) \quad (6)$$

Experimental curve equation can be written as :

$$y(\alpha) = (T/T_{0.5})^2 [(d\alpha/dt)/(d\alpha/dt)^{0.5}] \quad (7)$$

where $y(\alpha)$ is the mechanism function. $F(\alpha)$ and $f(\alpha)$ are the reaction models. $d\alpha/dt$ is obtained from TG curve. When experimental curve overlaps with the standard curve in plot of $y(\alpha)$ versus α curves, the corresponding $F(\alpha)$ or $f(\alpha)$ is being taken as the most probable mechanism function.

From the TG curves of synthetic zirconium phosphate, it is quite evident that process of thermal changes occurred mainly in two steps under non-isothermal condition. The basic data of α and T were collected from the TG curves of thermal decomposition of zirconium phosphate at different heating rates (5.0, 7.5 and 10 K min^{-1}) and presented in the Table 2.

According to FWO approach, $\log \beta$ versus $1000/T$ graphs at different heating rates were plotted for different fractional conversion values as shown in the Fig. 5. It was observed that $\log \beta$ vs $1000/T$ gave rise to a straight line relationship. From the slope of the straight line, ac-

Table 2. Correlative data for drawing plot $\log \beta$ vs $1000/T$ for step 1 decomposition of synthesized zirconium phosphate

α	β (K min^{-1})		
	5 (T/K)	7.5 (T/K)	10 (T/K)
0.2	351	369	376
0.3	358	375	384
0.4	363	381	392
0.5	367	387	399
0.6	372	394	407
0.7	377	401	416
0.8	382	410	426

tivation energy values along with correlation co-efficient (r^2) for the thermal decomposition of zirconium phosphate were calculated for α -values varying from 0.2–0.8.

It is widely accepted that the activation energy will be independent of alpha, when relative error of the slope of the straight lines obtained by FWO equation is less than 10%. Nevertheless, in such case, the decomposition may be regarded as simple reaction. However, if the relative error exceeds 10%, the decomposition process may be considered as multi-step reaction mechanism.

In this study, the variation in activation energy for the 1st step decomposition and the 2nd step conversion versus alpha values exceeded 10% and hence, the decomposition of zirconium phosphate followed a multi-step reaction mechanism. The average activation energy and correlation coefficient (r^2) results for the 1st step of thermal decomposition of gamma zirconium phosphate by FWO method were given in the Table 3. It may be noted that FWO method is not applicable to compute the activation energy for an exothermic reaction.

Figs. 6 and 7 presented the Kissinger plot of the synthesized gamma zirconium phosphate sample based on data from Table 4. From the slope of the straight lines, the activation energy values of the prepared gamma zirconium phosphate for the 1st step and 2nd step were determined to be $33.73 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $1037.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively (Table 5).

Thus, activation energy obtained by FWO and Kissinger method for the 1st step was 25.94 ± 4.9 and $33.73 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. Similarly, the activation energy was computed as high as $1037.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ by Kissinger method for the 2nd step of solid state reaction of synthesized zirconium phosphate.

Fig. 5. FWO analysis for the thermal decomposition of zirconium phosphate precursor (step 1).

Table 3. Activation energies (E_a) and correlation coefficients (r^2) for step 1 decomposition of synthesized zirconium phosphate calculated by FWO method

α	Step 1	
	E_a (KJ mol ⁻¹)	r^2
0.2	29.74	0.9905
0.3	29.06	0.9949
0.4	27.72	0.9970
0.5	26.51	0.9972
0.6	24.69	0.9973
0.7	22.81	0.9969
0.8	21.04	0.9949
Avg. value	25.94 ± 4.90	0.9955

Table 4. Peak temperatures used for drawing $\ln \beta/T_{\max}^2$ vs $1000/T$ K⁻¹ according to Kissinger method

T_{\max} (K) in three heating rates (K min ⁻¹)	Step 1	Step 2
5.0	368.8	1229.3
7.5	387.0	1233.6
10.0	398.4	1237.6

Table 5. Activation energies (E_a) and pre exponential factors (A) for decomposition of synthesized zirconium phosphate calculated by Kissinger method

	Step 1	Step 2
Activation energy (KJ mol ⁻¹)	33.73	1037.62
$\ln A$	-2.033	93.74
r^2	0.9978	0.9970

Therefore, the final step of conversion exhibited very high activation energy in comparison with that of first step which distinctly revealed that crystallization of amorphous zirconium pyrophosphate occurred at a sluggish rate and hence the rate determining step. Interestingly, the average activation energy value obtained by FWO method as well as by Kissinger method for the 1st step was close to each other so that the results were credible.

The classification of kinetic models based on plots of $y(\alpha)$ versus α for the determination of reaction mechanism for solid state reaction may be available from the Table 6. In determining the probable reaction mechanism for thermal decomposition of zirconium phosphate, α values from TG data of zirconium phosphate at the heating rate of 5 K min⁻¹ have been chosen and corresponding $y(\alpha)$ values were calculated. Then, $y(\alpha)$ values versus α were plotted as shown in the Figs. 8–10. Experimental curves based on eq. (7) for various reaction mechanism models were also drawn by the dotted lines and finally compared with theoretical curve to find out the best fitting model. As clearly evident from Fig. 8, thermal decomposition of zirconium phosphate sample for the 1st step is fitted exclusively with the contracting volume kinetic model (R3).

Fig. 6. Kissinger plot for the thermal decomposition of zirconium phosphate precursor (step 1).

Fig. 7. Kissinger plot for the thermal decomposition of zirconium phosphate precursor (step 2).

Fig. 8. $y(\alpha) - \alpha$ curves for the reaction mechanism model A2, A3, A4, R2 and R3.

Fig. 9. $y(\alpha) - \alpha$ curves for the reaction mechanism model P2, P3 and P4.

Fig. 10. $y(\alpha) - \alpha$ curves for the reaction mechanism model D1, D2 and D3.

Table 6. Classification of kinetic models for reaction mechanism¹²

Kinetic classification	$y(\alpha)$
(1) Sigmoidal α - t curves	
Avrami-Erofeev (A2)	$2(1 - \alpha)[- \ln(1 - \alpha)]^{1/2}$
Avrami-Erofeev (A3)	$3(1 - \alpha)[- \ln(1 - \alpha)]^{2/3}$
Avrami-Erofeev (A4)	$4(1 - \alpha)[- \ln(1 - \alpha)]^{3/4}$
Prout-Tompkins (B1)	$\alpha(1 - \alpha)$
(2) Acceleratory α - t curves	
Power law (P1)	$n\alpha^{(n-1)/n}$
Exponential law (E1)	α
(3) Deceleratory α - t curves	
(3.1) Based on geometrical models	
Contracting area (R2)	$2(1 - \alpha)^{1/2}$
Contracting volume (R3)	$3(1 - \alpha)^{2/3}$
(3.2) Based on diffusion mechanism	
One-dimensional (D1)	α^{-1}
Two dimensional (D2)	$[- \ln(1 - \alpha)]^{-1}$
Three dimensional (D3)	$2/3(1 - \alpha)^{2/3}[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3}]^{-1}$

Conclusions

From above investigation the following conclusions may be drawn

- (i) Zirconium phosphate hydrogel in gamma form can be derived through aqueous phase interaction of zirconium oxy chloride and dilute phosphoric acid at pH 2.5.
- (ii) The thermal transformation of sol-gel derived zirconium phosphate in static air under non-iso-

thermal condition is observed to proceed via multistep reaction mechanism.

- (iii) Activation energies obtained for 1st step of thermal dehydration by FWO method and Kissinger method are observed well consistent.
- (iv) Malek method confirms that the thermal decomposition of synthesized zirconium phosphate is accomplished by the contracting volume kinetic model (R3).

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